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China Bound, A Guide to Academic Life and Work in the PRC. by Anne F. Thurston, Karen Turner-Gottschang and Linda A. Reed. National Academy Press, Washington, DC, USA. 1994. pp. xii + 252. Price \$24.95 (paperbound). [ISBN:0-309-04932-6]

Cross-cultural exchanges call for certain amount of getting to know the other culture even before one leaves one's home country. The Americans, with their penchant for standardizing, usually hold a programme lasting for a few days for overseas scholars, especially students, wherein the visitors are told how to make their stay in the USA productive and enjoyable, how to get along happily in society, what to do and what not to do under different circumstances, etc. For most countries in the world, a few days of preparation

is all that one would need. But China is different, for various reasons. As one researcher says, being prepared in China can mean 'the difference between a headache and a productive day'!

This revised version of a much acclaimed book, originally published in 1981 and rewritten in 1987, is a comprehensive guide to scholars and scientists visiting China - first-time visitors and 'old China hands' alike.

To the American mind, China, though fascinating, is curiously ambivalent. It at once evokes the images of Marco Polo and Genghis Khan, rapid economic development and Tiananmen Square, friendly people and a frustrating bureaucracy. Added to these contrasting images is the language barrier, the vastly different social and cultural mores, and the totally different ways in which academic and scholarly institutions function and are administered.

It is to facilitate overcoming these barriers for the ever-increasing number of American scholars who are visiting China since the 'opening up' began in 1979 that this book was written. However, the material provided will be of great use to visitors from other lands as well to those who want to go and live, work and learn in China. This friendly and practical book offers all the details academic and other visitors need to make long-term stays in China productive, comfortable and fun. It covers everything from how to obtain

the correct' travel documents to the things to take care of before one leaves China after one's assignment there is over. Frank discussions on the research and academic environment in China, aspects of human relations (including possible romance with a Chinese citizen!), negotiating the costs of services, and a host of other equally important things make this book a truly invaluable guide.

The book provides useful information on science and social science field work, living costs, health care, addresses and fax numbers of important institutions and services, currency, transportation, communication, children's education, etc.

Yet another good point of the book is the large number of quotes from people who had lived and worked in China in the recent past.

There are 17 appendices and an index.

Anyone going to China will find this volume enormously useful. The Committee of Scholarly Communication with China deserves appreciation for commissioning this book as well as the two earlier versions.

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